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An architecture and platform for Multimodal Transport Management within the MODALSHIFT project

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Abstract

Efficient multimodal transport management is critical to reduce congestion, improve sustainability, and enhance operational efficiency in European cities and logistics hubs. The MODALSHIFT European Union-funded project addresses current issues like tool over-segmentation and lack of stakeholder coordination by developing a unified architecture and platform that integrates real-time, anonymized data from diverse sources, including IoT devices, transport operators, and infrastructure networks. Leveraging digital twins, AI-driven forecasting, agent-based modelling, and predictive analytics, the platform enables coordinated planning, operational control, and scenario testing across freight and passenger systems.

Implemented in three European case studies, the Port of Trieste (Italy), the Municipality of Varna (Bulgaria) and Madrid's Estación Sur (Spain), MODALSHIFT aims at demonstrating improved interoperability, optimized resource allocation, and reduced delays, while providing replicable methodologies, governance models, and data-sharing frameworks. The project introduces innovative use cases such as Capacity-as-a-Service, E-Subscriptions for vulnerable users, and cooperative incident management, supported by a multi-layer functional architecture comprising Data, Optimisation, Applications, and Use Case Layers.

A-to-Be plays a central role in the project, by delivering the Cooperative Management application, integrating operational and forecasting data, optimisation recommendations, and stakeholder coordination into a single interface. Building on results from the TANGENT EU funded project, A-to-Be ensures real-time situational awareness, collaborative incident response, and operational decision support, while exploring the integration of dynamic pricing and incentive mechanisms. By combining advanced data management, predictive analytics, and operational tools, MODALSHIFT illustrates a practical pathway toward sustainable, efficient, and user-centric multimodal transport networks in diverse urban and logistics contexts.

Keywords:

Multimodal Transport Management; Mobility Data Space

Introduction

Efficient and sustainable multimodal transport remains a major challenge in European cities and logistics hubs, where

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freight and passenger flows are increasingly complex and interdependent. Current transport management systems often operate in silos, typically targeted at specific transportation verticals, with limited integration between infrastructure operators, logistics providers, and public mobility services. This fragmentation results in suboptimal resource use, delays at intermodal connections, underutilized capacity, and environmental impacts. Moreover, the lack of reliable, real-time, and anonymized mobility data hinders decision-making and prevents the adoption of innovative solutions such as predictive traffic management, synchro-modality, or dynamic pricing and incentive schemes. Addressing these gaps is essential to support a transition toward greener, more efficient, and user-centric transport networks.

MODALSHIFT is a HORIZON European Union funded project which responds to these challenges by developing a unified architecture and platform for multimodal transport management that integrates data from diverse sources, including IoT devices, transport operators, and infrastructure networks. By leveraging digital twins, AI-driven forecasting, agent-based modelling, and predictive analytics, the platform enables coordinated planning, operational control, and real-time decision-making across freight and passenger systems. Implemented in three European case studies (the Port of Trieste, the Municipality of Varna, and Madrid) the platform aims to demonstrate improved interoperability, reduced delays, optimized resource allocation, and enhanced sustainability, while providing replicable methodologies and governance frameworks to support wider adoption of data-driven multimodal transport management.

The MODALSHIFT project

MODALSHIFT aims to build a trusted and valuable framework for local stakeholders by integrating and processing data from infrastructures, logistics and mobility operators. It delivers a multimodal transport-network and traffic-management optimisation system that supports collaboration and smarter decision-making [1].

At the heart of MODALSHIFT is a Mobility Data Space [2] that ensures secure, anonymised sharing of fine-grained geolocation data — putting data firmly at the core of the project. This trusted data infrastructure will be deployed in three real-world case studies in Bulgaria, Italy, and Spain, enabling local infrastructure, logistics, and mobility operators to exchange information in a controlled environment. To complement the collection of this multisource data and enable actionable experiments beyond what is already in place in the case studies, MODALSHIFT introduces new Internet of Things (IoT) devices — including a “smart box” that enables Capacity-as-a-Service and an “E-Subscription” device to facilitate public-transport access for vulnerable users.

Once collected, the data will feed AI-driven predictive and prescriptive analytics, as well as synchro-modality-based simulation scenarios, all tested within digital twins of the local transport networks and in early pilot deployments. These models will allow the project to detect events (e.g. disruptions) more accurately (targeting a 15 % increase in detection rate), forecast traffic states, and recommend optimal operational actions to reduce interconnection or transshipment delays by up to 25%. Agent-based modelling will simulate how a shift toward low-carbon, active, and shared mobility could work at the behavioural level, helping to design public transport services, logistics and urban spaces in ways that are acceptable and attractive to end-users.

All of this is brought together by a unified planning, management and operational platform: a multimodal traffic-management system layered on top of the data space. This platform orchestrates cooperation among stakeholders (at network and hub scales), connects dynamic optimisation algorithms to tools used by mobility operators, and links static planning models to visual interfaces for transport planners.

Governance mechanisms, stakeholder value modelling, dynamic pricing, and business-model innovations are co-designed with up to eight stakeholders per case study — ensuring that the system not only supports efficient mobility

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but is also aligned with local needs, incentives, participation and is ready for future actions going beyond optimisation. With this approach, MODALSHIFT stimulates new uses of the transport network to reduce traffic congestion for low-carbon and inclusive mobility, avoiding pernicious rebound effects.

MODALSHIFT implements three complementary case studies across Europe — the Port of Trieste (Italy), the Municipality of Varna (Bulgaria), and the Estación Sur (South Station) in Madrid (Spain) — to demonstrate how data-driven approaches can optimise multimodal transport networks for both freight and passengers. These locations span the continent from east to west and present diverse contexts in terms of technological maturity and data availability, from Varna’s emerging digital infrastructure to Madrid’s extensive metropolitan network. Each case study leverages real-time, multisource data, digital twins, and AI-driven analytics to improve interoperability between transport modes, namely by coordinating operations at key hubs, forecasting traffic and demand, and implementing innovative solutions such as Capacity-as-a-Service and dynamic scheduling. Together, they provide practical insights, replicable methodologies, and governance models for advancing sustainable, efficient, and user-centric multimodal mobility.

The Trieste case study focuses on optimising multimodal freight operations in a major European logistics hub. As Italy’s top cargo port and the Mediterranean’s largest oil terminal, the Port of Trieste processed over 12,000 trains in 2023, connecting national and international networks and linking Austria and Slovenia with Adriatic and Eastern European cities. MODALSHIFT will enhance interoperability between waterways, rail, and last-mile transport by improving real-time data exchange among port authorities, national rail infrastructure (RFI), and logistics operators. Integrating with existing systems, implementing digital twins, and AI-driven simulations, the project will forecast traffic patterns, coordinate shunting and train schedules, and dynamically manage disruptions. The outcomes will provide best practices for regional rail operators and highlight environmental benefits from more efficient port operations.

In Varna, MODALSHIFT targets sustainable urban mobility for a city of one million residents, where seasonal population surges and limited urban planning tools challenge public transport and freight efficiency. The first use case enhances low-carbon urban freight by integrating the city’s cargo-bike fleet into a “pay-per-use” platform, enabling small businesses to reserve bikes and generate data for traffic-flow analysis. The second use case focuses on improving intermodal connections, redesigning schedules for buses, trains, and active mobility options, and establishing a data space and digital twin for better planning and forecasting. By raising data literacy and integrating new data streams into legacy traffic systems, the project supports a long-term shift toward green logistics, reduces emissions, and provides a replicable blueprint for other municipalities.

The Madrid case study addresses multimodal passenger and freight transport across a metropolitan region of 6.7 million residents, with a focus on the southern districts and key hubs like Estación Sur. MODALSHIFT will build a digital twin of the city’s transport network, integrating open mobility data and additional sources to optimize inter-city bus routes, schedules, and on-demand mobility options. At Estación Sur, a unified system will facilitate real-time data exchange among stakeholders, enabling dynamic adjustments to operations, coordinated passenger services, and a Capacity-as-a-Service model for freight. The results will be designed for high replicability, allowing other public transport operators and municipalities to adopt the platform and improve efficiency, reliability, and sustainability across their networks.

MODALSHIFT will build directly on several key results developed by the Horizon 2020 TANGENT project [3], most notably the TANGENT Dashboard and its advanced forecasting models. The TANGENT project already

An architecture and platform for Multimodal Transport Management within the MODALSHIFT project established a mature, web-based decision-support tool that integrates real-time monitoring, anomaly detection, and short-term traffic forecasts (5–60 min horizon), supported by deep-learning and graph-based predictive models [3]. By reusing and extending these forecasting modules and web-based tool, MODALSHIFT will accelerate its deployment of AI-driven predictive analytics in its three case-studies.

Beyond forecasting, MODALSHIFT inherits TANGENT's architectural principles around data governance, multi-actor cooperation, and dynamic incident-management. TANGENT developed a data-sharing governance model for multimodal mobility data [4], as well as “response plan” capabilities in its dashboard to simulate and manage disruptions in real time [5]. MODALSHIFT will build on these by integrating its own data space (with anonymised geolocation data, IoT devices, etc.) into a unified platform that uses TANGENT's decision-support logic but adapts it to its three case studies (Bulgaria, Italy, Spain).

Finally, by leveraging TANGENT's proven tools, MODALSHIFT can focus more quickly on its innovation frontier: layering agent-based models, synchro-modality scenarios, and dynamic-pricing strategies on top of a solid operational core. This reuse helps MODALSHIFT minimize risk, cut development time, initiate testing and evaluation earlier in the project schedule, testing during a longer period, and more effectively deliver its vision of a unified, multimodal, and optimised transport management system.

An Architecture for MODALSHIFT

This section has a dual purpose. It describes both the basis of the architecture which will be adopted in this specific project but aims to propose a reference architecture for projects managing multimodal transport and shifting drivers and passengers to more optimized modes.

The projects' functional architecture is broken down into four integrating layers. The Data Layer collects data and distributes it within the project partners; it also acts as the integration mechanisms between the different modules of the project. The Analytics and Optimisation Layer uses data to produce forecasts, analysis, hypothesis studies and recommendations. The integration of data and the functionalities of the Analytics and Optimisation Layer into the Applications Layer allows the project to implement a set of use cases depicted in the Use Cases Layer.

Figure 1 – MODALSHIFT functional architecture

In Figure 1, no interactions between modules are depicted to avoid over-complexity. Generally, the Optimisation and Applications Layers interact with the Data Layer to collect and exchange data. Modules within these two layers also interact between them using the Message Queue of the Data Layer. The Use Cases Layer is conceptual, providing a key functional view of the implementation and each use case functionality is implemented by a combination of applications.

The Data Layer is responsible for collecting data from external systems, namely open data sources and private stakeholders’ data. Different formats and data organisation will exist in the fetched data sources, data transformations in the Data Layer (such as aggregation, anonymisation, format conversion, and harmonization) are essential to ensure that diverse data sources can be integrated, securely shared, and efficiently processed across project partners. These processes enable consistent, privacy-compliant, and interoperable datasets, forming the foundation for reliable analytics and decision-making.

Instead of having different partners fetching and repeating the transformation process on their own, the project will adopt a single transformation pipeline for each data source, sharing the resulting data through two main mechanisms. A Data Space will be implemented to provide adequate data management and governance for private stakeholders’ data. The Data Space will catalogue and manage access to data, ensuring that data does not leave its owners, guaranteeing full sovereignty over any shared data. Open data, in contrast, does not require these kinds of measures, any partner could fetch it, except this would be duplicating work, especially when each partner might have to transform this data, converting its format, aggregating it and anonymising it. To avoid this, a Message Queue was selected as a complementary data

sharing mechanism to the project's Data Space. The Message Queue will receive all fetched and transformed open data in the project. It will also be used to communicate between the project modules, namely, to activate models in the Optimisation from Applications and to receive their results. Live and processed data can be fetched directly by subscribing to Message Queue topics, whereas Historical data will be stored in an auxiliary filesystem. Message Queue topic naming and historical data file naming will be done according to project-wide definitions and access to data will be controlled through access control lists and authentication, achieving an adequate level of data governance, still below that of the Data Space. The Data Space can be a sophisticated solution, requiring the definition of many aspects regarding the data handled. Even the initial step of injecting new data items into an existing Data Space can be challenging. More concretely, the Sovity Connector is the main component included in the toolkit that enables the participation in the Data Space. The Sovity Connector [7] is a lightweight, standards-compliant implementation of the International Data Space Connector specification that facilitates participation in data spaces. Developed to align with the architectures promoted by IDSA and Gaia-X, the Sovity Connector enables organizations to share and consume data in a trusted, sovereign and policy-compliant manner.

This is unnecessary for Open data which is free from access control mechanisms and is usually catalogued in a rather ad-hoc manner, using web documentation, examples and sometimes REST APIs. This justified having a simpler, more ad-hoc, Message Queue mechanism, which still offers access control and many other security features, but is intrinsically simpler than the Data Space. The Message Queue will also act as an accelerator for private data sharing within the project from an early stage, when the Data Space will not yet be available due to the complexity of its initial definition and setup. Data sources initially shared with the Message Queue will, in time, be migrated into the Data Space, achieving a higher maturity in data governance involved.

The Optimisation Layer offers several distinct forecasting, analytic and simulation models that use specific data elements from the Data Layer to produce their results. Most models require training; this is usually done using representative sets of historical data. To cater to this need, the project is preparing to start collecting historical data from an early stage. When data sources only contain live data (very common for most open data sources), the Data Layer will implement a storage mechanism that saves all fetched live data in the Historical Storage filesystem.

The Optimisation Layer will include forecasting models which use historical and real-time data, graph neural networks, and transfer learning to predict traffic flow and detect anomalies in transport systems. On the simulation side, this layer will include agent-based, activity-based, and digital twin models that enable detailed simulations of transport systems, scenario analysis and the evaluation of mobility and logistics strategies. These models can also implement optimisations by simulating various scenarios and adjusting parameters to identify the most effective transport strategies or configurations. Through dedicated optimisation and heuristic models, this layer will offer direct solutions for complex planning problems, such as dynamic route planning and capacity booking, quickly generating feasible and efficient solutions under operational constraints.

The Optimisation Layer will implement digital twins for some of the use cases. By processing real-time data and providing both forecasts and scenario-based results, the modules in this layer implement a typical digital twin architecture where the real-time status of a digital twin is extended with future states predictions and scenarios can be explored within the digital twin to determine the impact of specific optimisation measures. The Message Broker can act as the element holding both the real-time state of the digital twin and the produced data for forecasts and the results of simulating specific scenarios. Digital Twins typically have message queues at their core for state

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representation and exchange, and this fits perfectly with the proposed architecture for MODALSHIFT.

Coming to the Application Layer there is an Operations group where IoT devices enable E-Subscription and Smart Box & Locker use cases and integrate with an IoT Gateway which integrates the devices with the platform using the services of the Data Layer. The E-Subscription use case will be a low-power IoT device that can be used by vulnerable users. It can provide a seamless onboarding and offboarding experience in public transport and can track these users and warn them and other transportation elements about safety risks. This will not only ease the life of vulnerable users but can also save their lives in situations like wheelchair users moving around stopped buses, where they can be totally invisible to drivers. The Smart Box & Locker uses other types of IoT devices to implement Capacity-as-a-Service for small scale freight using available capacity in buses.

The Fleet Management application in the Operations group will implement the Cargo Bikes and Fleet Optimisation use cases. The Fleet Optimisation will be implemented in the shunting activities in the Port of Trieste where it will improve delays and service disruptions and automate their communication.

In all previous use cases, which are mostly operational, by integrating with the Data Layer, the IoT devices and Fleet Management application, will also provide enhanced situational awareness and multimodal data integration across the transport ecosystem by means of the Management and Planning components of the Applications Layer.

The Cooperative Management application will provide live and forecasted situational awareness in all the case studies, spanning all use cases. It will also include cooperative features like chat and cooperative incident management, where, building together with functionalities from the Optimisation Layer, it will be possible to interface with stakeholders from the case studies and interactively prepare and activate optimisation plans. The live and forecast situational awareness functionalities will be used to monitor the results of activating optimisation plans.

The Planner application will be the main interface with the Simulation and Scenario tools within the Optimisation Layer. It will bring tools for transport planners to enhance decision-making: from data analysis to what-if simulation, giving access to easy-to-use agent-based-modelling simulation, providing both simplified and more sophisticated simulation results.

Finally, the MODALSHIFT platform also plans for a Pricing and Incentives application which will be conceptually explored and planned for in the project, although there is no implementation or planned trial for it. This module has a key role in adopting project results at a later stage. While many optimisations can rely on coordinating services, changing service scheduling or capacity and conveying recommendations to passengers and drivers, the most impactful changes may only be achievable by changing behaviours outside of the operational, tactical and strategic control of the operators. These changes will require not only the optimisation tools but also mechanisms to influence passenger and drivers' options. This Pricing and Incentives application brings exactly that mechanism, bridging optimisation modules to actual pricing and incentive mechanisms applied to users, through apps, dynamic pricing or other adequate means.

A-to-Be's Role in MODALSHIFT

A-to-Be plays a relevant role in MODALSHIFT by delivering the Cooperative Management application, the project's main operational interface for tactical and operational multimodal transport management across all three case studies. This application provides live and forecasted situational awareness, enabling operators and stakeholders to jointly understand current conditions and anticipate near-future events. It also supports cooperative features such as real-time chat, collaborative incident management, and interactive preparation and activation of optimisation plans. Once Optimisation Layer modules propose an action, the Cooperative Management application becomes the environment where stakeholders validate, execute, and monitor its effects in real time.

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Within the case studies, A-to-Be deploys a unified management solution adapted to each local context. In Trieste, the system consolidates port operational data, allowing operators to easily understand the current state of rail-maritime processes and act proactively using forecasts. In Varna's second use case, it provides city-wide situational awareness, enabling operators to focus on specific districts, integrate seasonal variations, and manage both planned and unplanned events. In Madrid's second use case, it enables comprehensive monitoring of Estación Sur, integrating relevant multimodal-hub data so that operators can manage daily operations and exceptional situations supported by predictive insights.

A-to-Be also ensures seamless integration across MODALSHIFT layers. Working with partners in the Optimisation Layer, A-to-Be incorporates forecasting outputs, decision-support algorithms, and optimisation plans directly into the operational interface, enabling enhanced incident management and coordinated multimodal responses. At the same time, A-to-Be integrates live data streams from the Application Layer, including IoT devices, digital-twin services, and other operational systems. These integrations ensure that the Cooperative Management application becomes the central, real-time hub that connects data, forecasts, optimisation recommendations, and stakeholder coordination into a single operational environment for multimodal transport management.

A-to-Be brings to the MODALSHIFT project the features of the TANGENT project Dashboard [6]. The TANGENT Dashboard is focused on the intuitive visualisation of transport data, offering a fully customizable multi-tenant dashboard where allowed users can easily configure visualisations for existing and new data sources.

Figure 2 - TANGENT Dashboard screenshot showing the city of Rennes (France)

The TANGENT Dashboard shows live and forecast data in either Map or Key Performance Indicator (KPI) widgets, as illustrated in Figure 2. Map widgets can combine several different data sources into a single display while KPI widgets focus on a single aggregated measurement. Colour and symbols are widely used to intuitively depict the network status. The generic nature of the technology behind the TANGENT Dashboard is not limited to transportation data and can easily scale to other kinds of data. Even in transportation it is frequently necessary to display related data from other domains. In TANGENT it's possible to filter data and focus widgets in specific geographic areas or

An architecture and platform for Multimodal Transport Management within the MODALSHIFT project corridors, both for maps and KPIs, allowing for the easy creation of more specialized and focused dashboards, tailored, namely, for Incident Management. By being able to easily add new data sources and visually configure them, the TANGENT dashboard fully empowers agencies, operators and emergency services.

A key feature in the TANGENT Dashboard is the possibility to prepare Operational and Tactical Response Plans, for example to cope with a football match or with a flood situation. These Response Plans use simulation and/or AI technology to evaluate the key situation and provide an optimized action plan that can be triggered. Actions can include changing scheduling or capacity of transport network elements, adapting traffic light control plans or other relevant actions over elements in the transport network.

These plans can be created and managed cooperatively by multiple stakeholders. Cooperation is also supported by built-in chat features in TANGENT. These Response Plans can then be monitored automatically using KPIs defined from the available data (for e.g. the current travel time for a route or measured water levels) and are able to trigger an incident once the Response Plan needs to be activated. This initiates Incident Management which allows the activation of the action plan and uses the TANGENT Dashboard visualisation features to allow operators to monitor the resolution of the situation, either for an entire city or focused on a specific area, depending on the incident.

The TANGENT Dashboard was developed by A-to-Be as a functional prototype within the TANGENT project, although it is very close to being a product, there are still some gaps.

For MODALSHIFT A-to-Be considered the best course of action would be to integrate the functionalities of the TANGENT Dashboard into A-to-Be's Advanced Traffic Management System (ATMS) which is called Atlas. Atlas brings with it more operational features such as Incident Management and Response, IoT integration including video camera visualisation and control and integration with message panels and other operational devices. These operational features may become available to the case studies and by providing a full product ecosystem with features such as high availability, Atlas will be able to deliver a better experience for the case studies while making sure the features developed within the MODALSHIFT project can be exploited from within one of A-to-Be's market products, able to reach a higher Technology Readiness Level (TRL).

A-to-Be is also responsible to explore how Dynamic Pricing and Incentives would best integrate the MODALSHIFT platform and be integrated into valid Business Models.

Conclusions

The integration of the TANGENT Dashboard's innovative data visualisation and operational planning features into A-to-Be's Atlas Advanced Traffic Management System marks a significant step forward for the MODALSHIFT project. The ability to intuitively visualise multi-source transport data, prepare and monitor tactical response plans, and leverage real-time KPIs enhances the capacity of agencies and operators to manage complex transport scenarios efficiently. The cooperative functionalities, such as built-in chat and multi-stakeholder plan management, further enable seamless collaboration during incident management and operational response, thereby improving overall system resilience and adaptability.

By embedding the TANGENT Dashboard's capabilities within the Atlas platform, A-to-Be not only addresses the gaps between prototype and product but also elevates the Technology Readiness Level of the solutions developed under MODALSHIFT. The inclusion of operational features like IoT integration, video surveillance, and control of message panels creates a comprehensive ecosystem that supports both immediate operational needs and long-term scalability. Furthermore, the exploration of dynamic pricing and incentives within this framework opens up new pathways for sustainable business models and

An architecture and platform for Multimodal Transport Management within the MODALSHIFT project encourages behavioural shifts among transport network users, reinforcing the project's broader objectives of modal shift and enhanced mobility management.

Overall, the work presented demonstrates the value of cross-project synergy and the importance of flexible, user-centred platforms in addressing the evolving challenges of modern transport networks. The approach taken by A-to-Be and the MODALSHIFT project illustrates how advanced digital tools, grounded in real-world operational needs, can deliver practical benefits to cities and stakeholders, supporting both daily operations and strategic transport planning.

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